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REVIEW ARTICLE

Holistic View of Pandemic in Integrated Environment: New Variant of COVID Surge in the USA with Holistic Environment Participation in Creating Future More Aggressive Mutants

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ABSTRACT

Planet Earth is a little one, and on one side it hosts the continents and on the opposite side is the Pacific Ocean, where the dry land represents 29%, from which 30% are deserts and 20% are mountains, while 50% is used for human activities. An integrated environment includes Earth and humans [1], as part of the Earth's fauna, and any living creature from few nanometers up the very large ones, having in common pursue of life. The recent planetary SARS-Cov-2 pandemic [2] placed a special stress on the planet, and placed in the lime-light the dominant characteristics and moral values of humans, their incapability to identify a real threat, adapt and prevail. Due to coarse incompatibility of moral values of various nations, with real life values, many nations ended up politicizing the pandemic and having inappropriate preparedness and response, and as a consequence they recorded high losses in human lives and standard of lives. Earth registers a record high of death, of about 7 Million from which USA worth only 4% of Earth's population contributed with an exceptionally tragic milestone of 1 Million deaths [3]. Due to inappropriate measures to stop the pandemic, the planet slipped into economic troubles as inflation and supply cycles disruption, that set a supplementary pressure to climate challenge, and for some with terrible moral values for which truth is their enemy, needed an escape goat to distract from the real economic and cultural problem and badly needed a new war, in an exacerbation of xenophobia, hypocrisy and misinformation [4]. This new calamity, has good chances of transforming into a nuclear war, where about 10,000 strikes of about 100 Mt-TNT might be applied to northern hemisphere [5]. In the present conditions COVID is embedded in the environment [6], with new variants due to pandemic as delta, O'micron and BA2, and few more, and from environment is given back to humans, and a new surge appeared in Europe with a delay of about 2 mo. from the elimination of all restrictions. This means that by April- May US will be infected again, with a new version escaping previously made vaccines. In the eventuality of a Nuclear War, ignoring the directly affected areas, the presence of heat and then cold, radioactive pollution, will trigger the gain of function of many passive, or dormant viruses, which will find a new ground of reproduction on the hoards affected by the exposure to nuclear warfare, and having handicapped immunity systems [7]. The survivors from the nuclear war will find difficult to survive to the pandemic with radiation enhanced novel viruses and functional structures.

INTRODUCTION

There is no secret that in the world there are hundreds of military and "confidential" bio-chemical laboratories, belonging to the world's powers, mainly western countries, placed all over the world, that are studying novel welfare agents inside the realm of these forbidden bio-chemical warfare WMD agents. By 2019 in the USA appeared a strange disease "EVALI" [8], used as argument to regulate the

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emerging market of e-vaping, guard railing the undesired competition, than by Dec. 2019 the novel COVID appeared in china, and soon after that on the entire world, being more aggressive than the Spanish Flu of 1917. Immediately US leaders put the blame on China's Wuhan Laboratory, they participated in funding the research there, while China pointed at Fort Detrick starting a new war of disinformation [9], while the truth remained unknown, while figure 1 shows a map for the USA military bases and bio-labs [10].

We will not ask the question of :”why Russia and China put their countries in the middle of US military bases and bio-labs, or who is in fact responsible for SARS-CoV-2 gain of function?”, humans or nature. Finally no-matter if the COVID gain of function [11], is a human achievement or it is the nature who suddenly build it in a favorable environment as a consequence of climate change, is less important when compare this with the capability of populations to detect, identify and develop the right procedures to protect against it. By the year 2020 after a strain of COVID was discover and erupted in China, and many other strains surged world-wide, with exception of few western pacific rim countries who managed to control the pandemic, almost all other countries failed to protect themselves and their citizens, following the lead of USA, where the pandemic took new aberrant dimensions outside the realm of medicine and science, being deeply rooted in politics and alternate

realities [12]. The protective measures in the EU and the USA were defiant to science, and the millennial experience with pandemics, starting from middle ages eruptions of cholera and bubonic plague, to the most recent Spanish flu or Ebola [13]. All these events and recent science contributed to the development of the hierarchy of Pandemic controls, which was proven efficient over the time and continuously improved, having clear effective controls [14]. To scientists dismay the authorities decided to add fictitious controls and ignore the real controls, and base the solution on a falsehood, praising vaccines as ultimate solution to pandemic. This was a blunt deception promoted in the name of big business, and western “civilization”, started investing massively in few preferred pharmaceutical companies, while avoiding to deliver a \$100B stimulus to small and medium business to improve and implement the means of pandemic control all over the US.

Figure 2 shows how China applied the pandemic control, near the ideal values, while US invented fake controls, with adverse effects, while ignoring or mishandling the real ones, and obtained the opposite effect, counting 81M infected, 11M long-haulers, and 1M deaths, out of 6M in the world. This is a representation of novel US exceptionalism as with only 4% of world's population the delivered 20% of causalities, by a factor of 5 over the world's average losses, and that put a big stress on US.

Figure 1 Bio-Labs and military bases around the world.

Figure 2 Hierarchy of pandemic controls applied in China vs. USA and ideal with results.

The problem is that in order a vaccine to be effective and terminate a virus spread, first the pandemic has to be stopped, in order to prevent virus to multiply and mutate, because after trapping and decoding a virus strain it takes several month until an effective vaccine is produced and distributed. Doing this under pandemic the vaccine will be always obsolete, or in “political perms”, the public is losing immunity in few months after vaccine application, and needs “boosters”, that to make the immune system be hyper-excited and attack anything in the body it may deem suspicious [15]. Finally \$ trillion have been spent at little to no avail, which cumulated over disruptions in economy and society, because a healthy economy with sick people is a falsehood. In the USA the use of mask was not really understood or was ever well explained to population, and took a deep political flavor, therefore the map of political leaning was almost similar with the map of COVID infections, as figure 2 shows. During republican reign 1/2 Million deaths was registered and 40 Million infections [16]. After 2021, when on Jan. 6 due to travel restrictions Americans organized the “Coup d’état” attempt at home, the democrats come into power and replaced the republican incompetence and corruption with a democrat one, and the good trend obtained during 2021 spring was compromised by CDC mask restriction lifting by May, for political reasons, without the overpraise vaccination heard immunity to be

reached, and a new surge in COVID cases and death occurred, called “the pandemic of unvaccinated”, and not only, and new restrictions have been put in place up to O’micron mutant occurrence, when things slipped out of control, and O’micron as a wild fire “burned” anything it had access to, inside a tribal laminar US society. Soon after O’micron’s peak was reached, many EU countries lift any restrictions also for political reasons and in a response time of 1-2 months COVID surge happened again for the 6th time, without any “lesson learned”. For more details see the cases in Germany, Korea, EU and the beginning of the surge in the US, this time with BA2 string and other mutants waiting to be baptized.

On this background US was under inflation stress, simply because the monetary mass released was not in synchronism with economy, due to different political stands, as tax cuts; COVID stimulus that overheated the stock market transforming it into a casino, oil and energy disruptions under climate change inflicted damages, and economy disruption under various COVID waves, made new president approval rating sunk. On the accumulated pressures a main factor was the real IQ factor of populations [17], because this finally defines the brain power of a nation, and its position in world’s economy [18]. For example China having IQ = 104.5 adjusted after COVID test at 100 and a population of 1.4 Billion has a total brain power of 140 GIQ; while USA with a population of 1/3 Billions and an IQ = 98, adjusted at 68

after COVID test has a total brain power of 21 GIQ, by a factor of 7 under China and a factor of 4 under India, and about a factor of 2 under EU, and the transition from unipolar world dominated by NATO and US is taking place right now, when US lost the world leadership, it gained grace to 1940's atomic bomb, and is still wants to use military power and deception to deter and slow down the other countries development, by initiating planetary turmoil and wars. The recent war in Ukraine was initiated by forcing Russia to attack Ukraine in order to defend itself against a future NATO aggression using middle range nuclear hypersonic missiles [19].

By 2019 US withdrew from most of the treaties, as seen in development of short and middle range nuclear hypersonic missiles a few \$Trillion business for the military industrial complex. As in a chess game, pinning Russia with 2 bad choices, as a war now against a 40 Million people, Ukraine, or a war in 3-4 years against a 1 Billion people NATO US and EU were able to stir the war in Europe in a very bad moment, from pandemic point of view. To this the destruction and pollution of the environment is added, as main ingredients of a catastrophic humanitarian and environment problem. In the context of western hypocrisy, breeding in population Russo/Chino phobia, with plenty of double standard in western mass media – similar to media under communist dictatorship makes the majority of population look for alternate sources, like Q, and others anchored in alternate realities, with deep disrespect for science pedaling on a large variety of conspiracy theories, and pushing down the capability of these nations of sticking together and protect against the real enemies of the human civilization. The first danger is at the Ukrainian-Polish border where various COVID carriers intermingle and transmit various mutant strains each other, where miseries of pandemic surge is adding to the refugee life hardships, maximizing the diversity of aggressive bio-agents, being absolutely incompatible with vaccine usage to control it. In these circumstances only engineered control might be efficient, as presented in figure 4. But in the context of war stress, propaganda misleading and alternate information sources, for a population with IQ presented in figure 3 these methods of simple basic protection remain out of reach, and a double tragedy will unfold.

A big unknown at the Euro-American equation is the role of environment in storing and propagating the virus. Without commenting on criminal action of Biden- Stolenberg, who hired the “servant of people” con-artist, and pushing with grandiose hypocrisy and deception, him in taking a patriotic “stunt”, ending with flattening of Ukraine, and stimulating business of the USA of about \$200Billion/year at a cost of 50,000 Slavic populations dead. Due to shelter and refugee agglomeration novel COVID found a beautiful ground for mutation and spreading in Europe at the very beginning, starting by next month with a surge over a surge that by the mid-June will be in the US too. Figure 2 shows a block of flats, with vents from urban unconventional Figurant, where is no

secret that when one uses a javelin or RPG from an apartment will attract the artillery fire, with the associated destruction. When an apartment is pulverized by an explosion the possible virioli present there are spread I atmosphere and most of them are destroyed due to high pollution. Some of the virioli that become airborne may survive for days depositing as fog in the morning on the surfaces of ground and vegetation. The vegetation may be ingested by the wild life and virioli find a place to multiply and mutate. Figure 5 also shows super-spreader opportunities offered by war inflicted pain, highlighting in center almost all social life transmission paths.

Surrounding environment action as a reservoir and source of stored virioli enhanced by local fauna that also get infected entering in contact with humans' residues and exhausts, as food, waste water, sewage, land fields, and more recently in Ukraine in destroyed homes [20]. In these cases they will store and carry the virus, mutate inside their body, spread in the heard of animals and flocks of birds and transported across the land and delivered back to humans. Nature opens a very intricate multiple paths, multi-dimensions.

Following the recent development a high pressure is put on politicians by various sides for their own gain, as Ukrainian actor acting for Biden with respect to new arms or direct involvement in a “no fly zone”, under the umbrella of nationalism, ignoring a eastern Europe saying, that “the dog jumps at the height of the stick” or translated, better weapons stiffer resistance will lead to more causalities and destruction, just remember Trump who delivered a MOAB over Afghanistan, with high impact on environment there or US delivering “green agent” over Vietnam in disregard to Geneva convention or Environment protection. Now it is about a possible nuclear war, this year or a decade later, because many under-educated politicians in power in western countries do not understand the intricate details and they are prone to push the military-industrial complex agenda that will be a \$1Trillion/y business to fabricate several thousands of short/medium range hypersonic missiles equipped with nuclear warheads, probably W-88s. Re “evil” countries will respond and do the same, and because the time of flight is less than 5 min. the response will be commissioned to computer system, which I about 2 min. will launch the response, at least an order of magnitude over the initial detection, and so on. In this scenario it is possible that few hundred charges of about 1/2 Mt-TNT will be blasted each day, delivering Earth about 1 PWh/day, warming the planet by 10 -20 deg. and rapidly changing the environment. This may happen also using the actual ballistic missile stocks as shown in figure 6. Due to blast nature, a lot of micro-particulates will be shot in upper atmosphere changing its temperature distribution. The radiation background will become heterogeneous varying from several Sv/h down to μSv/h creating vaster conditions for mutations in any living being from flora to fauna. Virioli may be affected too and get

Figure 3 IQ factor of various nations corrected after pandemic response.

https://www.amazon.com/COVID-19-protection-based-nano-bio-engineering-ebook/dp/808189RHGC/ref=sr_1_1?dchild=1&keywords=Papa-Simi&qid=1602865037&sig=ditag1-text&sr=1-1

Figure 4 Comparative view of engineered protection efficiency various vaccinations.

Figure 5 The devastation and particularities of war and environment role in COVID accumulation and spread.

Figure 6 Effects of nuclear war on virioli and integrated environment.

some gain of function, and in few mo. the “nuclear winter” will come for about 50 years, with disastrous consequences.

As we saw in figure 6 the integrated environment and virioli propagation will be drastically modified by adding to the already very complicated “equation of pandemic”, the new stimulus brought by drastically changing the environment by nuclear means. In figure 7 we show just a tiny slice on the impact of population movement due to Ukraine war disaster. In figures are given in rectangles the actual number of war refugees, entering neighboring countries, some of them being contagious with COVID, interacting with the local populations which dropped any protection measure few weeks ago. It is common sense that in these new conditions the new population influx will generate a future surge in COVID. As one may see in the charts with data Dec. 12 2021; Jan. 18; Feb. 24; ($\Delta t = 36$ day, about 5 weeks). The red star is placed synchronously with the peak in UK, and it is uses in rest of charts to show the delay of about 1 mo. to other omicron peaks occurred in Europe. The green star shows the moment restrictions were lifted and in western world is seen the rejuvenation of pandemic in countries like Finland, Germany, Switzerland, Italy and France. Of a special interest is Ukraine, where due to war the reliability of data is affected, on which new waves of mercenaries around the globe are coming from west and Russians and others coming from East, and if proper conditions for testing and reporting

might be put in place, an increase in contagiousness may be detected, as a surge in cases. On the other hand more than 3 Million people have been dislocated becoming war refugees, carrying with them the eastern virus mutation. One may not imagine that delta, omicron, BA2, variants were the only strains that occurred and were so successful from the very beginning. The moment they have been identified and named, they were already the result of a natural selection, and in the very moment there are hundreds of strains of viruses in each part of the planet, under natural selection. We have to see now central Europe under the action of two main waves that trend to interfere and create a tsunami pattern: one from NW, with the trigger given by the green star and one from East, driven by migration flux, and a little composite component driven by the inflow of foreigners and supplies in Ukraine. The problem is that from the point of view of integrated environment this is a disaster, to the destructions of war, under a psychosis of nationalism, independence and perverse persuasion of the west inciting low IQ population to more pain and destruction, for the sake of business based on unfair competition. You see from here that biological entities are not the single enemies of humanity, even in the case of COVID, after person cures, inside the body remains sub-entities producing various symptoms, from early dementia, to brain malfunction, muscle damage, fertility. As one to understand, inside the body of a delta or o’micron virioli, that may be approximated to 100–120 nm sphere, may break

Figure 7 The effect of Ukraine war refugees and people traffic on SARS-CoV-2 evolution.

in 216 entities of 20 nm of the size of common flu, or 125 of 25 nm, or 64 of 30 nm or a combination of the above, say 50–100 Nano-bio-functional-entities in a cocktail with delayed action as function of momentary inside the body conditions, and this may be the biggest challenge in actual medicine. The novel conditions introduced by a nuclear planetary war, which become more possible than ever do to natural selection of leading class excelling in incompetence, arrogance and greediness, which may be considered internal brain diseases, more dangerous than COVID nano-machine, and with no real cure, but WWII, will exacerbate the competition for survival among all mutants from flora to fauna, and will end up in a drastic change of integrated environment. In a holistic comprehension the Earth will run the deices again to generate another integrated environment in the next 100 Million years.

CONCLUSION

After 6 waves of COVID tsunami, most of the planet has no lesson learned; human kind is more exposed than ever to unknown effects of COVID long term consequences.

COVID and actual politicians showed the entire spectrum of weakness and malfunctions in the human society that is impacting directly the entire planetary eco-system.

In the struggle for hegemony, and under pressure from inside, mainly to accumulated historical tensions and superficial education, with low, duplicity moral and ethical values, low IQ, US tries to preserve the world leadership, even with the price of inciting and participation to world's environmental damage.

It is useless that we developed world class science to help confronting any pandemic if the population under continuous exposure to state driven hypocrisy, double standard and deception promoted by all mass media outlets, lost trust in science and education, being unable to connect the dots and discriminating between real life threats and profit and population control based freedom infringement, as have been seen during these two years under SARS-CoV-2.

In order to end the war, western powers have to do exactly the opposite of what they did to provoke the war, and negotiate with the Russians the mutual security guarantees, reverse NATO's expansions, stop interfering and organizing "coup d'état" all over the world, accept and integrate in

multi-plural planet, and promote a hypocrisy and deception free external politics.

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